

How Flexitime Improves Employee Efficiency: A Case Study of Private Organization in Karachi – Pakistan

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Abstract:

The flexible working is always welcomed by the employees and when we talk about the organizations who are involved in information technology business; these trends are very popular and fascinating. This article provides specific study and research that local information technology firm has found that flexible working time progresses employee's efficiency and growth in the organization productivity.

Key Words: *Flexitime, Employees' efficiency, flexible working time.*

1.0 INTRODUCTION

Flexitime can be defined as the flexible working schedule of the employee. As compared to the standard working time in an office which is 9 a.m. to 5 p.m. in a day flexitime offers employees to work as per your desired working schedule. Almost half of the total working time, the employees are expected to be at work while for the remaining half, the employees can choose when they want to work depending on their daily tasks and assignments.

Two types of policies are associated with this idea; one is flexitime while another one is flex place. Flexitime allows employees to decide when they will work and flexplace determine employee where they will work. Another arrangement in the flexible work includes flexibility in the number of hours worked.

Inflexible working, the employees can have the opportunity to control their working space, time and duration. Previously, every employee must assure their presence in office during their working time, but now they have the opportunity to decide with flexible timing, work from home and reduce working hours.

The study would find out how employees' efficiency will get improvement from flexible working timings. How flexitime directly impacts on your employee's performance with respect to the quantity of work, quality of work, teamwork & retention. Further, we will also discuss how flexitime in-directly impact on your performance with respect to job satisfaction and organizational commitment.

1.1 PURPOSE OF THE STUDY:

The purpose of the research is to analyze how flexible working time stimulates employee's efficiency in an organization who are primarily intricate in information technology business.

1.2 JUSTIFICATION OF THE STUDY

- This research would be beneficial in refining flexible working practices of an organization.
- The research progresses the knowledge of flexible working time and its implementation of the similar type of organization.

2.0 DISCUSSION:

To determine how the flexitime improves employee efficiency, a survey has been conducted in Karachi. the company mainly involves information technology projects. In this survey, the formal interview has been planned with different employees and try to find out how flexitime progresses employee's efficiency.

The importance of flextime has been highlighted by many employees especially in some circumstances, the employees' efficiency has been improved. On the other hand, flextime can also create a problem for the organization in terms of discipline and management.

Most of the organization who are involved in information technology works are mostly have clients abroad. They must follow certain timings as per the client requirement. Due to flextime, these timings can be managed in very effective manner.

Some of the positive signs of flexible working for management are as follows:

2.1 IMPROVED EMPLOYEE MORALE:

It has been observed that the employees who have control their in and out time are very much relaxed and happier, but this may create some discipline issue in the organization. HR department may get trouble by organizing each employee's flexible timings.

2.2 REDUCED ABSENTEEISM:

Flexible working gives employees to avoid absenteeism. Most of the employees take their casual day off when they have an appointment with doctor / dentist or parent's teacher meeting of their children. With this flexible working schedule, they have a chance to arrive at work later.

2.3 REDUCED OVERTIME:

The staff overtime can be avoided by giving them the opportunity to work with flexible timings. Employees can manage their workload with respect to their schedule, and it will cope better with busier and slack periods.

2.4 WORK-LIFE BALANCE:

Flextime provides healthy work-life balance to their employees. The stress full routine, de-motivation and un-pleased work life are always burden to the organization. The health and sickness cost may increase in un-balance work life.

2.5 REDUCED EMPLOYEE STRESS:

A research has been carried out by City University showed boosted job control of employees who have going through flexible working. The greater job control will ultimately reduce employees stress. Employees are more happy and comfortable when they have fully command on what they are doing at its workplace.

2.6 EMPLOYEE TURNOVER:

The employee turnover can be controlled with the provision of flexible working. Employees depart in cases where they are not fit with the company's working timings and space. Flextime allows them to work as per their desired time and environment.

2.7 TIMELY JOB COMPLETION:

Most of the employees love to complete their task in time, and this can only be possible if they are willing to complete the assigned task in a specific time. When you are working on a project, and it can take more time in a day, but you have to take off due to office timings. In flextime, you can manage your time as per the assigned tasks, and if they can take more time to finish, you can invest more. In a fixed working daytime, this can't be possible.

2.8 EMPLOYEES EMPLOYER'S RELATIONSHIP:

The traditional concept of face management in which employers are keen to watch their employees to confirm the work in their working space has been replaced by flexible working. In the new era, this old-fashioned concept has been swapped with the organization far-sighted approach. Employers have only interest in their timely completion of work. This new concept is strengthening the relationship between employees and employers.

2.9 BETTER COMMUNICATIONS:

Employees working schedule has been shaping up as per the requirement of the organization. It can be reflected in improved communications where everyone in the organization acknowledges the availability of workers at the crucial stages.

2.10 COMBATING WEATHER CONDITIONS:

Unexpected and extreme weather conditions counter the availability of employees in their working space. Recently floods and a hurricane in the USA proved the importance of flextime, most of the workers work from their home during this hurricane. The bad law and order situation allows workers to work from their home without any excuses.

2.11 TECHNOLOGICAL ADVANCEMENT

In this era, the technological advancement facilitates us with teleconferencing and cloud computing. The employees interact and speak with their client and their office colleague any time from their home. The cloud computing allows employees to use office servers and other related data from the internet.

However, flexible working has some negative consequences observed by the employees.

3.1 MISUSE OF AUTHORITY

Most of the employee's misuse when they work from home. Flextime allows them to use their times as they want. Office employees work as per the policy of the organization. they have to maintain discipline.

3.2 FAMILY ENGAGEMENTS

Family engagements are one of the ways where employees also misuse their authority during flextime. Work from home gives a message to the employees' family that they are on vacations. Employees are confused and dislike to engage their times with family during flextime.

3.3 WORKING FROM HOME

The phenomena of load shedding are very common in our society. The research reveals that employees are badly affected by the load shedding when they work from home. Employees don't have electricity backup at their home as compared to their offices with proper electricity backup.

4.0 RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

The strategy used in this survey was comprised of a set of research questionnaire. The research personally interviewed with the 25 number of employees (both management and technical) working in the technical department of local information technology company. This company already offers flexible working for its employees.

4.1 RESEARCH QUESTIONS:

Q1: What type of flextime your company is offering to the employees?

Q2: Do you think that flexitime directly impacts on employee's performance with respect to the quantity of work?

Q3: Do you think that flexitime directly impacts on employee's performance with respect to quality of work?

Q4: Do you think that flexitime directly impacts on employee's performance with respect to teamwork?

Q5: Do you think that flexitime in-directly impacts on employee's performance with respect to job satisfaction?

Q6: Do you think that flexitime in-directly impacts on employee's performance with respect to organizational commitment?

4.0 CONCLUSION OF THE STUDY

The following conclusion has been drawn from detailed analysis of the study.

4.1 QUANTITY OF WORK

The quantity of work is directly related to the state of mind an employee could be in. Humans, being part of social systems, bring quite a lot of challenges on the day to day basis. If those challenges are not addressed in a timely manner, it influences the persons of state of mind, and that causes a direct effect of an employee's 'Quantity of work.' The study revealed the importance of flexitime and its impacts directly on employee performance with respect to the quantity of work.

4.2 QUALITY OF WORK

Quality of work is also very much dependent on the state of mind. A peaceful state of mind will bring a good concentration to the work an employee is performing thus a quality is greatly improved.

4.3 TEAMWORK

Flexitime, also influence good Teamwork. If a certain member of the team needed to finish a personal work which will make him available with the peace of mind, a flexitime would influence the Team to shuffle the work around and make the whole team available with great state of mind. If the flexitime is not available, and everyone has to be available at a certain time no matter what, the employee will either find out an excuse to skip the work or will be available without a great focus on the job which will, in turn, cause the friction in the team and will affect the teamwork.

4.4 RETENTION

Flexitime definitely helps the retention. The employee will feel comfortable to address the personal situation and will always give this a plus point for the company to continue working with.

4.5 JOB SATISFACTION

It may - only if the Flexitime is being abused. The abuse of flexitime will cause to develop redundancy of thought process which in turn could create a lousy outcome of the work performed. But this situation is an exception.

4.6 ORGANIZATIONAL COMMITMENT

The organization creates the policy around the definite availability and always have a backup plan to supplement the work.

5.0 RECOMMENDATION:

The flexible working hours are proven their importance day by day. Fresh graduates always try to get those jobs which are most suitable for their working hours. They don't like the way where the organization is matching their performance evaluation with the strict company policies.

There is now need to re-defining organizational culture with shrewdly integrating flexible working hours. The organization will adopt output-oriented approach instead of traditional employment style. The employees are more focus on work efficiency and quality outputs rather than punctual arrivals. Flexible working will boost up employee's efficiency, performance, and loyalty towards work and besides ensuring discipline in the organization.

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